

HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME – TOPIC HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05

*Wind energy in the natural and social environment
Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

Grant Agreement No. 101083460

Starting date: 1st January 2023 – Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D5.1

Web-GIS interactive forum (a)

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable number	D5.1
Deliverable title	Web-GIS Interactive forum (a)
Work Package	WP5
Deliverable type¹	Document, report
Dissemination level²	Public
Due date	30.06.2024 (Month 18)
Pages	72
Document version³	4.0
Lead author(s)	Lien Bakelants, NAZKA
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The WIMBY project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

1 Type: ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot; R: Report; D: Demonstrator

2 Dissemination level: C: Confidential; P: Public

3 First digit: 0: draft; 1: peer review; 2: peer review 3: coordinator approval; 4: final version

DOCUMENT CHANGE HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description
DRAFT			
0.1	04.06.2024	Lien Bakelants, NAZKA	Creation
FIRST PEER REVIEW			
1.0	14.06.2024	Rebecca Hueting, DBL, Luis Ramirez Camargo, UU	Proofreading and peer review
1.1	17.06.2024	Lien Bakelants, NAZKA	Consolidation of input from reviewers
SECOND PEER REVIEW			
2.0	17.06.2024	Ides Bauwens, NAZKA	Second peer review
2.1	18.06.2024	Lien Bakelants, NAZKA	Consolidation of input from reviewers
COORDINATOR APPROVAL			
3.0	27.06.2024	Luis Ramirez Camargo, UU	Coordinator review
FINAL VERSION			
4.0	29.06.2024	Stella Arapoglou, VUB	Format review, version ready for submission

SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This deliverable describes the design and development process of the first version of the WIMBY interactive map and general forum. A design approach with co-creation workshops was adopted to maximise consortium partners and external stakeholders engagement and integration of their needs. The results of these workshops are described comprehensively and analysed thoroughly. Based on this input, the technical requirements of the WIMBY interactive map and general forum were gathered and prioritised for development. The development of the first web-based version of the WIMBY interactive map is described in detail. This first version is accessible with a link which is available on request.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
GIS	Geographical Information System
API	Application Programming Interface
GA	General Assembly
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
TSO	Transmission System Operator

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the key developments of WIMBY is an interactive map and general forum to enable a wide range of stakeholders to examine the different implications of wind farm development. The interactive map will provide access to multiple data layers and model results from the environmental and social impact assessments conducted in the WIMBY project e.g. land use change, noise, shadow flicker. The tool makes it possible to investigate impacts, enablers and constraints and the effect on the wind potential. It is tailored to be used both by expert users and the general public. The scope of this deliverable (D5.1) includes the design and development of the first working version of the WIMBY interactive map.

The WIMBY interactive map aims to integrate datasets and tools developed in work packages 1, 2 and 4. These datasets and tools will be used in the two main features of the WIMBY interactive map: the map layers and the wind farm simulation tool. For the first version, the focus was set on wind resource data and terrain data layers, made available by DTU (deliverable D1.2). For the wind farm simulation tool, the estimated energy production was shown, modelled by DTU (deliverable D2.1). The noise model of PSI was integrated to display the noise impact of the wind farm (deliverable D2.3) together with the regulation information gathered by KIE (deliverable D2.9).

This report explains the results of the different steps of the design process of the WIMBY interactive map and forum. First the target audience was identified, in a second step representatives of these groups were interviewed. In a third step user flows were co-created with partners which were then visualised in the form of wireframes. Feedback was gathered from partners during a wireframes feedback session. Finally, these comments were processed and an interactive prototype was developed. This prototype was then tested with the representatives. This input was used to list the technical requirements of the WIMBY interactive map. These requirements were then prioritised and utilised to develop the first version of the tool.

All the task objectives were achieved: a first version of the interactive map was designed and developed considering the needs of the stakeholders. In next steps, more datasets and tools will be added and the WIMBY interactive map and general forum will be tested with stakeholders to improve it further.

1. INTRODUCTION

An interactive map is a very powerful tool to visualise spatial data and make it possible to identify spatial relationships. It enables the visualisation of large amounts of data in an accessible way and makes it possible to receive information for a specific area of the user's choice. It can also act as a public participation tool, enabling societal engagement of challenges with a spatial component.

In task T5.3 "Web-GIS interactive forum co-creation and assessment (front-end)", the aim is to develop a web based interactive GIS platform to merge the results of the environmental, technical, economic and social assessments performed in the other work packages of the WIMBY project. It allows to visualise and download, amongst other things, spatial data of wind resources, impacts on safety and health, landscape quality impacts, collision risks, results from the LCA as well as data on regulations, funding mechanisms and potential job creation (outputs of individual tasks in WP1 and WP2). This is possible both on the continental scale as well as for a specific region of interest. The interactive map aims to translate the outcomes of complex models of environmental and social factors to understandable and useful information for the involved stakeholders. This is complemented with access to forum functionalities to enable stakeholders to find and exchange information to promote wind energy development.

Other tools exist that inform stakeholders about wind resource availability such as the Global Wind Atlas and the New European Wind Atlas. The WIMBY interactive map adds information that needs to be considered in the planning and development process about impacts (environmental, technical, economic and social concerns) and constraints (regulation, physical obstacles). Additionally, the WIMBY interactive map also targets multiple user groups to be able to involve less technical stakeholders.

To make sure the tool is useful for its stakeholders and achieves its goals, the project invests a lot in co-creation workshops. Not only consortium partners but also the advisory board and potential end users are involved in the creation of the tool.

This deliverable describes the design and development process for the first version of the interactive map and general forum. In the design process and data analysis, the vision for the final version of the interactive map was researched and envisioned. Concerning the development, the aim was to develop a first version with fully working core functionalities, but not yet including all the functionalities and datasets. An overview of these functionalities is shown in chapter 3.3.3 First version of the interactive map. In the second deliverable (5.2) more functionalities and datasets will be added to reach all objectives set for the tool.

This report starts with explaining the methodology followed in the design of the interactive map and general forum and which phases were completed to arrive at the first version. In the results section, an overview of the results for each design phase is outlined in combination with the technical analysis and finally the functionalities of the end product: the WIMBY interactive map.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Design approach

For the design of the interactive map and general forum, a methodology inspired by the design thinking approach is used. Design thinking is a process to empathise with users, confront assumptions, clearly define problems and come up with creative solutions to test (Friis Dam and Yu Siang, 2024).

The Design Thinking approach exists of 5 stages (see Figure 1):

- Empathise: empathise with your end users to understand their wants and needs
- Define: organise the info gathered during the first stage and define the problem very clearly in a human-centred way
- Ideate: come up with innovative solutions to the problem from different perspectives
- Prototype: identify and implement the best possible solutions
- Test: test the solutions with real users

Design Thinking: A 5-Stage Process

Interaction Design Foundation
interaction-design.org

Figure 1: Stages of Design Thinking (Source: Interaction Design⁴).

The Design Thinking methodology is not a consequential but a non-linear and iterative process. Later stages can loop back to earlier stages when new insights are gained, iterations are persevered until the desired level of maturity is reached.

2.2 Methodology for the WIMBY project

To arrive at the first version of the WIMBY interactive map and general forum, an approach with the following steps was used:

- Empathise & define:
 - o map and understand the stakeholders and their needs
 - o define the target audience and organise interviews with representatives
- Ideate:
 - o co-create user flows with consortium partners
 - o gather inspiration and brainstorm solutions
- Prototype:

⁴ <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/what-is-design-thinking-and-why-is-it-so-popular> (last accessed on 7.06.2024)

- create wireframes and gather feedback from consortium partners
- create interactive prototype and gather feedback from representatives
- Implementation & test: develop the WIMBY interactive map in iterative short cycles with testing sessions

This design approach was complemented with a technical and data analysis to make sure that the functionalities imagined in the design were also technically feasible and matched the available tools and datasets from the other work packages.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Co-creation

During the design of the WIMBY interactive map and general forum, a lot of effort was focused on co-creation with partners and other stakeholders. These activities are organised by Nazka Mapps and DBL, with support from partners. During all these activities, information was gathered with both the WIMBY interactive map and general forum in mind. A Miro board was used internally for the project partners to perform the co-creation sessions and document the results. In this report, the results are visualised with screenshots from this virtual whiteboard. An overview of the co-creation sessions is shown below in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of co-creation sessions organised for the WIMBY interactive map and general forum.

Date	Type of session	Participants	Chapter
June 13, 2023	Target audience workshop	Consortium partners	3.1.1
November 2023	User interviews	User representatives	3.1.2
December 20, 2023	User flow workshop	Consortium partners	3.1.3
January 25, 2024	Wireframes feedback workshop at GA	Consortium partners	3.1.4

March – May 2024	User testing prototype	User representatives	3.1.5
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3.1.1 Target audience

In the first stage, the aim was to empathise with the potential end users of the WIMBY interactive map and general forum. This makes it possible to design and implement the tool with the users in mind. To achieve this, an overview of all stakeholders was created, and it was decided which ones to focus on.

As a first step, during a target audience workshop with partners, all actors, groups or individuals who might be linked or interested in the development of a wind farm project were listed (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Stakeholders for the WIMBY interactive map and general forum listed during target audience session with partners.

In a second step, partners discussed on how to categorise these individual stakeholders.

In a third step, partners identified which of these user groups would directly use the WIMBY interactive map and general forum, by creating a bullseye canvas (Figure 3):

- Interested audience (local communities, pro and against wind activists,...)

- Ancillary businesses (businesses that benefit from wind farm development like lawyers, journalists, urban planners, consultants,...)
- Affected industries (maritime transport and fisheries, land developers and real estate managers, industries competing for land use,...)
- Specialised users (wind and non-wind researchers, transmission system operators,...)
- Education (teachers, students,...)

Bullseye canvas

Figure 3: Bullseye canvas to identify the direct users of the WIMBY interactive map.

In a last step partners prioritised the most important target users through dot-voting. Three user groups emerged as key users:

1. Interested audience (local communities, pro and against wind activists, landowners...)
2. Specialised users (wind and non-wind researchers, transmission system operators...)
3. Education (teachers, students...)

These priority groups guide us in later phases of designing and implementing the WIMBY interactive map and general forum. Additionally, by creating contacts with these groups, we ensured to receive their input and suggestions.

3.1.2 User interviews

With help from the partners, it was possible to identify and contact representatives of the 3 identified user groups. Together with Deep Blue, Nazka Mapps organised 7 remote interviews:

- Education group (2 high school teachers)
- Specialised users (2 experts in wind farm impact assessments, 1 Computer Science researcher, 1 employee of a TSO)
- Interested audience (1 landowner)

In preparation of the interviews, a script was created with some guiding questions. All interviews were recorded after consent forms were signed by the interviewees and extensive notes were taken.

A summary of the user interviews was presented to the partners by means of the Miro board together with the memorable quotes, challenges and opportunities of each interviewee (example in Figure 4).

Memorable quote:
"Give communities the feeling that they are promoting the transition themselves, and not something that is imposed upon them."

What about NIMBY?
 What does the user think about the NIMBY effect?

- maybe different for people who are not used to it
- it is caused by forcing things on people
- Who has the right to have an opinion on wind turbines?

Did the user ever encounter it?

- he is used to wind turbines (a lot of them nearby where he lives)
- and a lot nearby the land of his parents

CHALLENGES / PAIN POINTS
 What are the main challenges of the user?

- no excess capacity on electricity grid
- no expertise concerning wind farm siting
- he has to ask experts for help
- father thinks it is a waste to use good agricultural land for RE
- a lot of information is already out there, but you need to be an expert to manage it
- top down decision that is forced on locals
- creating a tool that does not make it look like there will be a forest of turbines (it is not the goal)

OPPORTUNITIES
 Which opportunities are indicated by the user?

- get information on regulations/ constraints
- do some fact checking (-> rely on info developers)
- explain impact to neighbours & other stakeholders
- visualize information in a clear way
- create transparency
- create connections between stakeholders
- a tool that is usable for non experts
- get info about the potential of your site

Figure 4: Example snippet from user interview summary with memorable quote, challenges and opportunities.

To empathise with the three user groups we tried to step in their shoes and brainstorm about some of their gains, pains and jobs to be done. Jobs to be done are tasks they need to complete in their day to day work or life. Gains are the benefits they could experience when using the WIMBY tools to finish these tasks. Pains on the other hand are the problems they can face or possible negative outcomes or difficulties.

The gains and pains are connected to possible gain creators & pain relievers in a value proposition canvas (Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7 below).

Figure 5: Gains, pains and jobs for interested audience group (Source: Strategyzer⁵).

⁵ <https://www.strategyzer.com/library/achieve-product-market-fit-with-our-brand-new-value-proposition-designer-canvas> (last accessed on 7.06.2024)

Figure 6: Gains, pains and jobs for specialised user group (Source: Strategyzer).

Figure 7: Gains, pains and jobs for education group (Source: Strategyzer).

3.1.3 User flows

All the gathered information from the empathise phase served as a foundation for creating the first design of the WIMBY interactive map. In the ideate phase, user flows were created to visualise each step a user needs to take while using the application to achieve their goal.

To work on the user flows, a co-creation session was organised using the Miro board with a group of consortium partners. In a first step, subgroups of the three main user groups are defined during a group discussion, together with their end goals. In a second step, each participant was asked to create a specific user flow individually. Finally, all individual user flows were combined together, which resulted in one complete user flow for each user group, including diverse partners perspectives. After collaborative refinement, the final user flows were consolidated.

Interested audience

For the interested audience group two subtypes were defined: landowners & energy communities. Landowners can either hear rumours about a project nearby or they are interested themselves in wind energy development on their land. They want to know the implications of it on their (and neighbouring) land and discover the WIMBY interactive map provides this info. The energy community on the other hand is looking for regions to expand its energy production.

After playing around on the WIMBY interactive map, the landowner wants to focus on their plot of land, the energy community on the other hand is less bound to a certain location and has a wider region of interest. They will both simulate a wind farm by drawing a polygon on the map and seeing the resulting layout, impacts and energy production. The landowner will focus more on different layouts on his/her plot of land whereas the energy community will also compare different locations. Both are interested in downloading a report and saving and sharing the simulations. The landowner will use this information as a basis for decision and/or engagement. The energy community is more likely to contact the WIMBY team for support and use the information for community planning and strategy development. The interested audience user flow is shown below in Figure 8.

Figure 8: User flow for the user group "interested audience".

Specialised user

For the specialised user group, it was decided to focus on Transmission System Operators (TSO) and researchers. TSO will most likely hear about the WIMBY project on a conference or from partners, the researchers will possibly find it through looking up papers & googling.

Researchers will be more likely to navigate to the documentation first, to make sure the data they need is available. TSO will quickly zoom in to a region or area of interest to view existing wind farms and energy outputs and the estimated wind energy potential for a certain region. Researchers will more likely consult the different map layers and perform a wind farm simulation. They will compare different locations and layouts and save the results. Both subgroups are interested in downloading the data either by selecting variables and formats in the interface or by doing requests to the API. When the data is downloaded the users have access to the metadata and can use the data for their models and projects. The specialised user flow is shown below in Figure 9.

Figure 9: User flow for the user group "specialised user".

Education

For the user group Education, two subgroups were defined: teachers (or more general people who explain things to others) & students (or people who will work with the map independently but can ask questions).

Teachers are seeking help or inspiration on how to explain wind farm siting and design to students. They find the WIMBY interactive map on the web.

They try to understand how to use the website by having a look at the user guide and the game. They come up with an assignment that compliments the theoretical explanation, and after explaining the theory, launch the assignment with the students. Students receive the WIMBY link from the teacher as well as the assignment and explore the WIMBY interactive map with the game. If needed they can ask questions to the teacher. They zoom in to a region of interest (e.g. to their neighbourhood) and try creating a wind farm. They compare different locations and layouts and save the simulations. They download a report and submit the assignment material to the teacher, who reviews their work. They present their findings to the class and get insights from the teacher. Finally, the student understands the differences and influencing factors of wind farm siting, and the teacher was able to explain a difficult subject to the students. The user flow for the education user group is shown below in Figure 10.

Figure 10: User flow for the user group "Education".

3.1.4 Wireframes

The user flows are an important starting point for creating the first sketches of the application, also called wireframes or low-fidelity prototypes. Wireframes are blueprints of the final web application, that represent the structure, navigation and functionalities. They are black and white static visualisations without too many details. They are an ideal format for quick adjustments and as such a great communication tool in the first stages of a project.

The first version of the wireframes, used during the feedback workshop at the General Assembly in January in Vienna, can be found in the ANNEX. In Figure 11 the screen for starting a wind farm simulation is shown as an example.

Starting the wind farm simulation

Figure 11: Example of wireframe screen for the wind farm simulation in the WIMBY interactive map.

The feedback workshop is designed to gather as much feedback as possible from the consortium partners in a limited amount of time. The workshop fosters co-creation by engaging the participants with writing sticky notes while navigating the different wireframes. The wireframes are divided into 4 “stations” inspired by the user groups (and one general station with more general functionalities):

- General station
- Interested audience station
- Education station
- Specialised user station

The participants were divided into 4 groups, starting at one of the stations and afterwards shifting to the next one. We asked the participants to give feedback in 4 categories:

- What do you like?
- What can be improved?
- Questions
- Ideas

The wireframes were shown providing a minimum explanation, this made it possible to check for the design team what was clear at first glance and what was confusing.

After gathering the feedback, each sticky note was jointly discussed and clarified. Participants could give more input and there was room for questions.

General station

In the General station the following wireframes were presented:

- Map layout (overall layout of the WIMBY interactive map with basic map features, the layer component, the menu, link to the user management...)
- About pages (static pages with more information about the project, datasets, help options...)
- User management (limited info that is gathered from users at sign up which can be edited later)

Interested audience station

In the Interested audience station, the following wireframes were presented:

- Starting the wind farm simulation (first steps to take to simulate a wind farm on a certain location)
- Wind farm simulation results (resulting layout, energy production and impacts of the simulation)
- Print report (possibility to render a pdf to summarize the results of a simulation)

Specialised user station

In the Specialised user station, the following wireframes were presented:

- Map layers (the layer component on the map with more options for each layer)
- Existing wind farms (a special layer with two levels: wind farms and turbines with more information and impacts)
- Downloads (multiple options to download data by choosing variables and formats or by using the API)

Education station

In the Education station the following wireframes were presented:

- Welcome & user guide (welcome pop-up when you open the WIMBY interactive map and interactive user guide)
- Game (game to introduce wind farm siting with scoreboard and goals)
- Saved simulations (possibility to open and share saved simulations)

In the ANNEX the most important outcomes for each station are listed, an example is shown below in Table 2. Pictures of the results of the workshop for each station can also be found in the ANNEX and an example is shown below in Figure 12.

Table 2: Feedback gathered for the interested audience station during the feedback workshop.

What do you like...	What can be improved...
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Symbols are easy to understand • The map gives info about available mean wind velocity, energy potential & various impacts of wind turbines • We like the layout in general • There is not too much info (no cognitive overload) • Nice summary report! • Regulations warning is super cool! To be added: date when info was obtained / reviewed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard constraints => should be blocked upfront • CO2 eq : results are per kWh delivered • LCA impacts: add bar chart for different stages • Add information (i) to map layer categories e.g. wind resource (i) • Compare with maximum in country or average in EU, or with country level energy output • Differentiate between positive & negative impacts • Polygon is not needed per se, user can also only indicate a point? • General public don't know what LCA is... Better to say environmental impacts/ impact on climate change (& others) • Amount of turbines is not needed as an input, which energy output does the user want is maybe better?

Questions	Ideas
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• What if we only know the area and not the number of turbines?• What happens if one wind turbine already exists when we add one manually?• Missing: timing of when the turbine is built? Important to know for LCA• How to compare my wind farm to existing one? Or to somebody else's simulation?• Can the user upload a custom polygon for turbine placement?• Does everyone know how to build a polygon?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Option to give a "nickname" to individual projects (saving and report)• Differentiate impacts between environmental and social• Show what area around that wind park benefits from it• Another option for turbine placement = equally spaced in the polygon• Divide / present impacts per life cycle stage (manufacturing, use...)• Show hard constraints (they are non-negotiable)• Exclusion zone "mode" to make sure user knows it is taken into account• Ask user level of complexity regulations in a certain area / country (questionnaire?)• Compare impacts to alternative energy source, now we only show "negative" perspective• Small summary comparison of 2 simulations?• Add / remove / move turbines• Spinner to show things are running (how long it will take)• Topography checkbox for shadow flicker• Show access roads (land use impact)• LCA info on existing wind farms• Add user-proposed exclusion zones?• Show also relatable / human centred positive impacts e.g. not only avoided emissions

Figure 12: Results of feedback workshop for the interested audience group.

3.1.5 Interactive prototype testing

The gathered feedback from the wireframes workshop was processed and considered as much as possible. After prioritisation and implementation of main recommendations, the next step envisioned testing more advanced prototypes with the user group representatives. Interactive prototypes were created with a look-and-feel closer to the final application to enhance the user experience. During these sessions, user behaviour observation during screen-sharing and aloud-thinking was executed to gather valuable feedback about user-friendliness, accessibility and the relevance of offered functionalities.

In preparation of the interviews, a script was created to guide the user through the prototype of the WIMBY interactive map and general forum.

Different prototypes of the interactive map were created for the different user groups to be able to focus on the most relevant functionalities:

- FIGMA prototype for the interested audience group⁶
- FIGMA prototype for the specialised user group⁷
- FIGMA prototype for the education user group⁸

Similar to the wireframe testing, a different combination of functionalities was selected for each target group involved in the prototype testing.

For the interested audience group, the wind farm simulation and the ability to share and save your simulations were chosen to be tested (Figure 13 and Figure 14).

⁶ <https://www.figma.com/proto/jhghJIJi6gry0Bo3RenKKW/WIMBY-map?node-id=3-256&t=I66qDAApWjW8cNzt-0&scaling=min-zoom&page-id=0%3A1&starting-point-node-id=1043%3A4475>

⁷ <https://www.figma.com/proto/jhghJIJi6gry0Bo3RenKKW/WIMBY-map?node-id=1043-4475&t=I66qDAApWjW8cNzt-0&scaling=min-zoom&page-id=0%3A1&starting-point-node-id=1043%3A4475>

⁸ <https://www.figma.com/proto/jhghJIJi6gry0Bo3RenKKW/WIMBY-map?node-id=174-3369&t=I66qDAApWjW8cNzt-0&scaling=min-zoom&page-id=0%3A1&starting-point-node-id=1043%3A4475>

Figure 13: Prototype that displays the results of a wind farm simulation.

Figure 14: Prototype screen that visualises how to share a wind farm simulation.

For the specialised group, the ability to download the wind farm simulation results was added (Figure 15). Another screen was made to show how the design team envisions a layer with existing wind farms (Figure 16).

Area 1
Nearest address
Area: 10 km²

Turbines: 3

Turbine types: small onshore

Soft Constraints

General Impacts **Download**

General

- Turbine locations (geojson)
- Area of interest (geojson)
- Energy output (csv)

Environmental impact

- Collision risk (csv)
- Land use change (csv)
- CO₂ impact during life cycle (csv)

Social impact

- Shadow flicker (tif)
- Noise impact (tif)
- Levelised Cost of Electricity (csv)
- Scenicness (csv)
- Accident risk (csv)
- Jobs (csv)

Download

Figure 15: Prototype of the download options for a wind farm simulation.

Existing wind farms

	<p>Nearest address</p> <p>Type: Onshore</p> <p>Capacity: 34 MW</p> <p>Operator: Nazka</p> <p>Start date: Oct 16 / 2012</p> <p>Years of service: 10 years</p>
	<p>Nearest address</p> <p>Type: Onshore</p> <p>Capacity: 34 MW</p> <p>Operator: Nazka</p> <p>Start date: Oct 16 / 2012</p> <p>Years of service: 10 years</p>
	<p>Nearest address</p> <p>Type: Offshore</p> <p>Capacity: 34 MW</p> <p>Operator: Nazka</p> <p>Start date: Oct 16 / 2012</p> <p>Years of service: 10 years</p>
	<p>Nearest address</p> <p>Type: Offshore</p> <p>Capacity: 34 MW</p> <p>Operator: Nazka</p> <p>Start date: Oct 16 / 2012</p> <p>Years of service: 10 years</p>
	<p>Nearest address</p> <p>Type: Onshore</p> <p>Capacity: 34 MW</p> <p>Operator: Nazka</p> <p>Start date: Oct 16 / 2012</p> <p>Years of service: 10 years</p>
	<p>Nearest address</p>

Figure 16: Prototype of the existing wind farms layer.

For the education group, we explored how to make the tool accessible for teachers and students by introducing a user guide (Figure 17). Additionally, a gamification approach was tested with two teachers to get feedback on

how to engage students (Figure 18: Prototype of the WIMBY game explaining what must be considered when planning wind farms by setting goals.)

Figure 17: Prototype of the welcome page with buttons to the game and user guide.

Figure 18: Prototype of the WIMBY game explaining what must be considered when planning wind farms by setting goals.

During the test sessions, also an advanced and operable prototype of the general forum was presented to the user representatives. Users were asked if they are familiar with discussion forums or commenting options. What would be their motivation in using such a feature and what would they expect to find in threads and discussions from other users? The collected feedback will be considered when creating the final WIMBY general forum structure and categories.

Finally, two different options for a connection point with the WIMBY interactive map were presented, to verify the reaction of the users' preferences (as usually done during A/B testing sessions).

Feedback on the different prototypes was collected during 7 remote user tests, organized by Nazka Mapps together with Deep Blue. The following target group representatives were interviewed:

- Education group (2 high school teachers)
- Specialised users (3 experts in impact assessments, 1 employee of a TSO)
- Interested audience (1 landowner)

The interviews were recorded and extensive notes were taken with signed consent of the interviewees. We use aggregated and anonymised data for the purpose of this research.

3.2 Data & technical analysis

3.2.1 Data inventory and bilateral data talks

The first data analysis was realised by UU, listing of all the input and output datasets needed and delivered by the WIMBY project. Such datasets are stored in the project YODA. To maximise mutual understanding, format alignment and interoperability, a "data-bazar" session took place during the General Assembly in Vienna on January 25 (Figure 18). This enabled all the partners to cross-check which inputs they would use from and share with other partners. Specifically for the WIMBY interactive map, datasets were identified that could add value when being visualised in the tool. This could be either as a layer on the map, or as a result of the wind farm simulation.

Configuration: Something that should be passed to the API as a variable from the user. This can be model parameters, results from a previous step, or additional data that the user must provide.

Input Data: Data that should be supplied on a full European scale, and subset to the area of interest. Examples are the NEWA microscale data, exclusion zone data, and elevation maps.

Model component / API: This is a single end-point for the modelling process. Each API call should take maximum around 50s to complete the modelling step, this means that we may want to make multiple API calls. Additionally, if you have some preparation that could then be used for multiple model configurations, making those separate API calls, so we can save the intermediate prepared data can improve performance.

Model Result: This is the data that is output from the model. In the example we use, these have been converted for use with the API, but it doesn't have to be at this stage. If a model result is an intermediate result, it can be passed into another model component via a configuration (green) arrow.

Figure 18: Template provided to each partner to present their data flow for "data-bazar" workshop.

To perform the technical analysis of the WIMBY interactive map, a better overview was needed of all the different datasets and tools that would be created by the different partners. Therefore, bilateral talks with these partners were organised to get a more clear view of their deliverables, the type of data or tools they produce and how this info can be visualised in the WIMBY interactive map. Each partner has the best insight concerning their own datasets and are best placed to give suggestions on how to visualise it. These cross exchanges will continue in the next stages of the project, as the datasets and visualisation options can still undergo changes coming closer to the final version.

3.2.2 Map and General forum integration

All the information gathered during the co-creation workshops and user interviews, is both valuable for the design of the WIMBY interactive map and for the general forum. Nazka Mapps, together with Deep Blue, analysed the input and a discussion occurred on how the cooperation should be organised. The needs of users concerning commenting and exchanging opinions with other users were thoroughly examined. Additional steps in the user flows were developed to analyse the potential links between the interactive map and general forum and guiding questions were used to identify solutions:

- When will a stakeholder use the WIMBY interactive map as an entry point?
- When will a stakeholders use the WIMBY general forum as an entry point?
- When will a stakeholder decide to shift from one tool to the other?
- Should a stakeholder using the WIMBY tool be aware or informed explicitly when shifting from the interactive map to the general forum, or not?

Observing user behaviour and discussing potential use cases internally, informed the proposed way of integrating and developing the two tools. Also, technical feasibility and time allocation were considered in this decision.

As a conclusion the team agreed that the WIMBY interactive map and the general forum would be developed as two different applications. Integration across the two digital environments will be ensured through a user-friendly link, allowing users to navigate easily from one tool to the other. The benefit of such kind of integration is that both tools can provide more advanced functionalities specific to the tool (like tagging and grouping conversations in the general forum), without interfering with the functionalities of the other (e.g. the limited space next to the interactive map or the different nature of visual and text contents and navigational style). In future versions, the ability to share a wind farm simulation created in the WIMBY interactive map on the general forum, for example to ask for feedback from stakeholders, will be investigated. Nazka Mapps and Deep Blue will keep working together to further analyse potential synergies between the two tools (e.g. login functionalities, customisations options and notifications).

3.2.3 *Technical requirements prioritisation*

Requirements are capabilities that a specific product or service needs to provide, in this case the functionalities of the WIMBY interactive map. These requirements are not fixed, following the agile methodology they are flexible and can change when more information is gathered throughout the project.

The requirements for the WIMBY interactive map were gathered during different phases of the project. Both input from external stakeholders and consortium partners was considered. In Figure 19 an overview of these requirements is shown in the shape of a mind map. Some of these

requirements still need to be investigated further, for example to ensure their technical feasibility.

The requirements are aggregated in groups to get a better overview in terms of types of functionalities:

- Help: functionalities that help the user navigate and use the map
- Wind farm simulation: one of the most important features of the tool, a way for users to request information about impacts, energy production and regulations and a simulation of turbine locations for a region of interest
- Pilot regions: information about the pilot regions of the WIMBY project
- About pages: information pages that explain the datasets and models that were created for the tool and other static pages like the terms of use, contact...
- Map tools: tools that make it possible to navigate the interactive map
- Languages: a way for the user to switch between different languages for the tool
- Existing wind farms: a map layer with more information about the existing wind farms
- Forum functionalities: this group contains both the commenting options that will be implemented in the WIMBY interactive map and the link to the general forum
- Map layers: spatially explicit datasets that were developed in the other work packages of the WIMBY project
- Downloads: functionalities to download different datasets on different spatial levels
- User account: authentication functionalities and extra options for users with an account like sharing and editing simulations

A similar mind map was used during a Work Package 5 meeting to select the target scope for version 1 of the WIMBY interactive map. This way, efforts could be focused on getting all the datasets and inputs ready for the implementation of these requirements for the first version. In the next chapter, the requirements and their status are discussed more in detail.

scrum methodology¹⁰. Both approaches focus on flexibility and short iterations to deliver a robust minimal viable product in a short period of time. By using a rapid prototyping approach both in the development of the map and the tools developed by consortium partners, it was possible to create first versions of the models quite fast and already implement them in a first version of the WIMBY interactive map.

The implementation is organised based on code-sprints of 1 week. Every week the development team assesses the status of tasks, new inputs and possible obstacles. This enables to quickly address arising issues or new inputs from partners. New implementations are tested regularly, and partners are shown the progress by means of a demo. Thanks to working in iterations, insights from previous sprints and testing are taking along in new sprints.

Thanks to regular meetings with Work Package 5 members, partners were kept up to date about the progress. DTU agreed to take care of integrating the tools and datasets and makes the result accessible through API requests. This way all the data and tools needed in the WIMBY interactive map can be smoothly accessed from a single access point.

3.3.2 Technical specifications

The interactive map is developed based on open-source technology, with a modular approach, starting from thoroughly tested existing building blocks. This enables spending time on a tailor-made design and functionalities that are customised following the identified needs of the user groups involved.

The JavaScript Library React¹¹ is used for the development of the WIMBY interactive map. It is a widely used framework with a vast community of developers and great additional libraries.

¹⁰ <https://www.scrum.org/resources/what-scrum-module> (last accessed on 07.06.2024)

¹¹ <https://react.dev/> (last accessed on 7.06.2024)

The WIMBY map makes use of the MapTiler¹² mapping platform. MapTiler supports and makes use of open-source technology and provides tools for creating custom maps. It is a good choice of mapping library for supporting both vector and raster tiles. It is suitable for web and mobile applications and specialises in customisation and design flexibility. Other services of MapTiler used in the WIMBY interactive map are geocoding (finding addresses) and custom background maps.

For the icons, the icon font library Font Awesome¹³ is used, for consistent iconography in the designs and implementation.

The WIMBY interactive map is built with an API based approach, both between the front-end and back-end of the interactive map and between the map application and the WIMBY server. Datasets and the result of the tools are requested by the map to the WIMBY API endpoints provided by DTU.

The WIMBY general forum application, currently running as a FIGMA prototype, will be based on the Discourse¹⁴ open-source platform, the theme .css customised to align with the WIMBY visual identity and contact points with the WIMBY interactive map ensured through cross-links. The possibility of adding API links across the map and the general forum will be explored for the next version of this deliverable and depending on its relevance and added value towards higher usability of the user interface and user experience quality (UI/UX).

3.3.3 First version of the interactive map

Version 1 of the WIMBY interactive map can be accessed via an open access link. This link can be offered on request. Both the WIMBY server and WIMBY interactive map are currently available on a test environment, as continuous development will take place in the coming phase of the project.

¹² <https://www.maptiler.com/> (last accessed on 7.06.2024)

¹³ <https://fontawesome.com/> (last accessed on 7.06.2024)

¹⁴ <https://discourse.org/about> (last accessed on 14.06.2024)

In Table 3, all the requirements are listed together with an indication of their status:

- Implemented in version 1: these requirements are implemented in the first version of the WIMBY interactive map
- Ready for implementation: these functionalities are ready for development but were not selected for the first version or the data or tools are not yet available on the WIMBY server, they will likely be implemented in the next version of the WIMBY interactive map
- Data not yet available: these requirements require the availability of a dataset that is yet to be delivered by a partner
- To be analysed: these requirements need to be investigated further as to how they can be visualised in the map

Table 3: Requirements listed for the WIMBY interactive map with their status.

Requirement group	Specific requirement	Status
Help	Welcome page	Implemented in version 1
	User guide	Ready for development
	WIMBY game	To be analysed
Wind farm simulation	Draw polygon	Implemented in version 1
	Input parameters	Implemented in version 1
	Edit input parameters	To be analysed
	Upload custom polygon	To be analysed
	My simulation info	Implemented in version 1
	Energy output results	Implemented in version 1
	Regulation warning	Implemented in version 1
	Noise impact on the map	Implemented in version 1
	Shadow flicker on the map	Ready for implementation
Accident risk	Data not yet available	

	Creation of jobs	To be analysed
	Scenicness	To be analysed
	Levelised Cost of Electricity	To be analysed
	Life Cycle Assessment	Implemented in version 1
	Land use change	Ready for implementation
	Collision risk	Data not yet available
	Download results	To be analysed
	Save simulation	To be analysed
	Print pdf report	To be analysed
	Compare simulation	To be analysed
Pilot regions	Pilot regions layer	Implemented in version 1
	Pilot regions local impact layers	To be analysed
	3D images for pilot regions	To be analysed
About pages	Introduction	To be analysed
	Methodology	To be analysed
	Terms of Use	To be analysed
	Datasets	To be analysed
	Credits	To be analysed
	FAQ	To be analysed
	Contact	To be analysed
Maptools	Scale & lat/lon coordinates	Implemented in version 1
	Zooming & panning	Implemented in version 1
	Search address & region	Implemented in version 1
	Change basemap	Implemented in version 1
	Zoom to my location	To be analysed
	Interactive legend	Implemented in version 1
Languages	EN, DE, PT, NO, IT	To be analysed

Existing wind farms	Existing wind farms layer	To be analysed
	Detailed information about wind farms	To be analysed
	Impacts calculated for existing wind farms	To be analysed
Forum functionalities	Link with General forum	Ready for development
	Comment on shared simulation	To be analysed
Map layers	Wind resource with height selector	Implemented in version 1
	Collision risk	Ready for implementation
	Scenicness	To be analysed
	Accidents	To be analysed
	Noise impact	To be analysed
	Hard constraints	Data not yet available
	Soft constraints	Data not yet available
	Regulations	To be analysed
	Terrain	Implemented in version 1
Downloads	Select datasets and parameters	To be analysed
	API access	To be analysed
User account	Sign up and login	To be analysed
	Edit personal info page	To be analysed
	Overview of saved simulations with share option	To be analysed

Below the requirements implemented in the first version are explained in more detail and illustrated with screenshots.

The first thing a user sees when opening the WIMBY map for the first time is the Welcome page (Figure 20). The user is welcomed with an introduction and the core functionalities of the map are highlighted. The user can close the welcome pop-up and access the WIMBY interactive map.

Figure 20: Welcome page of the WIMBY interactive map with an introduction to the core functionalities.

The map allows a user to zoom in and out and pan across Europe and to change the basemap from the default streets layer to a satellite view (Figure 21). In the left lower corner, the coordinates of your mouse on the map are shown, together with a scale (depending on your zoom level).

Figure 21: The WIMBY interactive map with the map tools and layers.

In the top right, a search bar opens when clicking on the search icon (Figure 22). This search functionality will enable the user to look for a certain region or address.

Figure 22: Search functionality that enables searching for a region or an address.

On the left side of the map, a map layer component is present that enables users to activate the available map layers. The layers are divided into categories to accommodate the long list of layers to be added in the next versions. For each layer, an info button is shown. On hover, an info text is displayed to give more information about the dataset (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Map layer component with available map layers and an info text.

Each layer can be activated by clicking, the checkbox will become active and the layer will load on the map. In the right lower corner, an interactive legend is displayed, to show the value of the dataset when you hover with the mouse over a certain area of the map (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Mean wind speed layer displayed on the map together with the interactive legend.

For the wind resource category, layers are available at 2 heights which can be selected with the height selector in the map layers component.

The pilot sites can be shown on the map by clicking the pilot sites layer (Figure 25). They are visualised with markers on the map, by clicking on them, the map zooms in on and visualises the boundary of each region. The side panel will slide open and a picture and some basic information are displayed.

Figure 25: Layer with general information on the pilot sites of the WIMBY project.

To start a wind farm simulation, a button is shown on the right lower corner of the map. This button only becomes active when zooming in enough, to make sure the user has a detailed view of the area they want to select. The active and inactive state of the buttons is displayed in Figure 26 below.

Figure 26: Inactive vs active state of “Start wind farm simulation button”.

After clicking the “start wind farm simulation” button, the user can draw a polygon on the map for an area of their choice (both onshore and offshore). After finishing the polygon, a pop-up is shown to select several parameters. The user can select the number of turbines and the turbine type (onshore, onshore low wind, offshore 10MW and offshore 15MW). The user can click on “run” to start the simulation and see the results (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Wind farm simulation parameter pop-up to start the simulation.

A spinner is shown inside the parameter pop-up to indicate the simulation is still running. When the simulation is finished, the side panel automatically slides open to show the results and the turbines are visualised on the optimised location inside of the user's polygon.

At the top, information about the user's wind farm simulation is shown: the closest address, the area of the polygon and the input parameters that were selected (Figure 28). Below two tabs are available: general information and information about the impacts. In the general tab, the estimated energy output is shown together with the calculated capacity factor for the simulated wind farm. Below information about the regulations is shown for both the minimal regulations in the EU, and the local regulations for the country or region (when available).

Figure 28: Results of the wind farm simulation on the map and in the side panel.

An info button with tooltip on hover explains to the user what is included in the regulations warning (Figure 29). The local regulations are only available for the partner countries in this version. Also, the date of these regulations is depicted. The following regulation info is displayed together with a link to the legislation documentation available online (when available):

- Distance to residential buildings
- Distance to motorways
- Distance to airports
- Distance to the coast

- Distance to transmission lines
- Distance to railways
- Distance to military areas

My wind farm simulation
Grenzweg, 74427 Fichtenberg, Deutschland
Area: 1.61 km²

Turbines: 3
Turbine type: onshore

General | Impact

Energy output
25.7 MWh

Regulation Warning

EU regulation
March 24 2024

For the area you selected, the following minimum regulations apply in EU countries:

- The distance to residential buildings should be turbine height +10% (find more info [here](#))
- The distance to motorways should be 30m or 0.5 x rotor diameter (find more info [here](#))
- The distance to airports should be 15 000m (find more info [here](#))
- The distance to the coast should be 100m (no link available)
- The distance to transmission lines should be 0.5 x rotor diameter + 60m (no link available)
- The distance to railways should be 1x turbine height (find more info [here](#))
- The distance to military areas should be 5000m (find more info [here](#))

Map Layers

- Wind resource
- Mean wind speed
- Power density

This section informs about the regulations that are active in the selected area both on EU level and local level in Deutschland - Baden-Württemberg.

Figure 29: Regulations warning shown in the side panel with info text in tooltip.

In some cases, no link is available because the information was not available online or the information was derived from another country with similar legislation if it could not be found.

In the impacts tab, a user can consult the noise impact and the environmental impact over the turbine(s) life (Life Cycle Assessment) (Figure 30). The noise impact can be activated by clicking the switch button. It will then load on the map with colours and labels showing the decibel

levels. The environmental impact in kg CO₂eq/GWh is calculated by using a life cycle assessment tool and the result is shown in the side panel.

Figure 30: Estimated impacts of wind farm simulation tab with the noise impact activated.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable D5.1 describes the methodology and preliminary results for the WIMBY interactive map and general forum, one of the tools to be developed within work package 5 of the WIMBY project.

Thanks to the co-creation workshops it was possible to design the WIMBY interactive map and general forum in a human-centred way. Insights were gathered about how potential users' gains can be maximised, pains can be relieved, and jobs can be enabled by using the tools of the WIMBY project. Combined with an analysis of the technical feasibility, priorities could be set to develop a first working version of the WIMBY interactive map. This first version demonstrates how the data layers and tools developed within the project can be transformed to API based resources for use in a web-based interactive map. Additionally with help from the partners we succeeded in visualising the outcomes of complex models in a user-friendly way.

In a next step, more datasets and tools will be added to the WIMBY interactive map interface. Afterwards, the interactive map will be tested with external stakeholders to analyse the user-friendliness and identify possible improvements. The aim is to develop multiple versions of the WIMBY interactive map to continuously improve the tool, add more of the requirements and integrate the map with the general forum. During the last phase of the WIMBY project, it is aimed to deliver an integrated WIMBY interactive map and general forum that allows both expert and non-expert users to investigate and discuss implications of wind farm siting all over Europe.

REFERENCES

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ANNEX

General station

Map layout

About pages

User management

<p>What do you like...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Good starting point• Looks user-friendly• Clean and intuitive web page• See existing wind farms from the start	<p>What can be improved...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• About pages: add how to work with the map, further links & publications and references• Allow users to add their own data• Difficult to know where to go for wind farm simulation• More user instructions!
<p>Questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Do we include info on user type while registering?• Can you also save datasets or only simulations?• Should we use the word "layer" to the general public?• Do we need a consent form?• Is it possible to show the current electricity production of the EU fleet?• Difference between layers and background layers?• Is the user account really necessary?	<p>Ideas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Embed WIMBY map in other websites• Can we have a welcome video on introduction page?• Link to WIMBY website• Add layer for legal/regulations info• Multiple languages• Descriptive title• Should the user be directed to NEWA or GWA for more wind data?• Add user type to account info for tracking purposes• Add story/overview of WIMBY history• Sign in with Google• Add methods and validation info of different tools to about pages• Show change in CO₂ emissions when adding wind farm

WHAT DO YOU LIKE?

- Good starting point already many good things! we agree!
- Color contrasts not over-extended
- clean and intuitive WP.
- see from the start the existing WP

WHAT CAN WE IMPROVE?

- More user instructions
- Search bar → zooming into your location
- More initial content on the map
- And pages - Add links into the content
- IS A USER ACCOUNT NEEDED?
- Wacky for much text - introduction - Start points - Size
- From the start page it is difficult to know what to do to explore the content
- the whole design looks horrible!

QUESTIONS

- What is special about existing wind farms? what will clicking do?
- How to Build My Own Farm? Run optimization design tool?
- Which info from the existing wind turbines will be presented?
- should we use the word "layer" to general public?
- difference between "Layers" and symbols?

IDEAS

- WIMBY EMBED
- Can we have a welcome video for the intro?
- Link to WIMBY website (to go back)
- Share projects option.
- ACCOUNT SHOW WHICH USER TYPE
- for the start show "did I do my own WP"
- Change in CO2 emissions if windpark is added
- ADD TOOL VALIDATION info

Interested audience station

Starting the wind farm simulation

The screenshot shows the WIMBY web-GIS interface. At the top, there is a browser address bar with the URL <https://map.wimby.eu>. The main map area displays a street map of Heverlee, Belgium, with a black polygon drawn around a specific area. A 'Select parameters' dialog box is open over the map, containing the following settings:

- Number of wind turbines: 3
- add turbines manually
- Wind turbine type: X
- Exclusion zones to consider: Multiple selected

Other interface elements include a 'Map layers' panel on the left with options for Wind resource, Impacts, Energy potential, Exclusion zones, Terrain, and Existing wind farms. A 'Menu' icon is in the top right, and a search bar is on the right side. A scale bar at the bottom right indicates 200km and 100km. A 'Funded by the European Union' logo is visible in the bottom left corner of the map area.

Wind farm simulation results

Print report

Print pdf 1 sheet of paper

Name :

Size :

Save Cancel

What do you like...

- Symbols are easy to understand
- The map gives info about available mean wind velocity, energy potential & various impacts of wind turbines
- We like the layout in general
- There is not too much info (no cognitive overload)
- Nice summary report!
- Regulations warning is super cool!
To be added: date when info was obtained / reviewed

What can be improved...

- Hard constraints => should be blocked upfront
- CO₂ eq : results are per kWh delivered
- LCA impacts: add bar chart for different stages
- Add information (i) to map layer categories e.g. wind resource (i)
- Compare with maximum in country or average in EU, or to country level energy output
- Differentiate between positive & negative impacts
- Polygon is not needed per se, user can also only indicate a point?
- General public don't know what LCA is... Better to say environmental impacts/ impact on climate change (& others)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amount of turbines is not needed as an input, which energy output does the user want is maybe better?
<p style="text-align: center;">Questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What if we only know the area and not the number of turbines? • What happens if one wind turbine already exists when we add one manually? • Missing: timing of when the turbine is built? Important to know for LCA • How to compare my wind farm to existing one? Or to somebody else's simulation? • Can the user upload a custom polygon for turbine placement? • Does everyone know how to build a polygon? 	<p style="text-align: center;">Ideas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Option to give a "nickname" to individual projects (saving and report) • Differentiate impacts between environmental and social • Show what area around that wind park benefits from it • Another option for turbine placement = equally spaced in the polygon • Divide / present impacts per life cycle stage (manufacturing, use...) • Show hard constraints (they are non-negotiable) • Exclusion zone "mode" to make sure user knows it is taken into account • Ask user level of complexity regulations in a certain area / country (questionnaire?) • Compare impacts to alternative energy source, now we only show "negative" perspective • Small summary comparison of 2 simulations? • Add / remove / move turbines • Spinner to show things are running (how long it will take) • Topography checkbox for shadow flicker • Show access roads (land use impact) • LCA info on existing wind farms • Add user-proposed exclusion zones?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Show also relatable / human centred positive impacts e.g. not only avoided emissions
--	--

Specialised user station

Map layers

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://map.wimby.eu>. The map displays a shaded area representing collision risk across Central Europe, including Austria, Slovenia, and parts of Germany and Italy. Major cities like Vienna, Salzburg, Graz, and Ljubljana are labeled. The interface includes a 'Map layers' panel on the left with the following categories:

- Wind resource**
 - Mean wind speed
 - Power density
- Impacts**
 - Collision risk
 - Species: [dropdown menu]
 - Opacity: [slider]
 - Scenicness
 - Accidents
- Energy potential**
 - Energy output
- Exclusion zones**
 - Hard constraints
 - Soft constraints
- Terrain**
 - Elevation
 - Ruggedness index
 - Bathymetry
- Existing wind farms

An information tooltip for the 'Collision risk' layer states: "The collision risk shows an estimation of the risk on birds & bats collisions calculated by the spatial distribution of species and collision data. You can select a species to see the collision risk for a certain species." The interface also features a search bar, zoom controls, a 'Menu' button, and a scale bar (0-200km).

Existing wind farms

Downloads

What do you like...

- Turbine info
- Easy to navigate
- Symbols are nice
- Overview of layers is good
- Looks easy to use / intuitive
- Nice information tab

What can be improved...

- Download per region
- Distance rules (regulations) + link to website (nat./region. level)
- Better/more descriptive wording for "hard/soft" constraints?
- The wind turbine icon is not super recognisable
- (i) should redirect to services or additional info
- Menu with background layers should be in another place (top/bottom)
- Financial compensation and participation for city / municipality layers
- Improve meaning icons & buttons

Questions	Ideas
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Difference between wind turbine icon with or without circle?• Scale: to which degree can the user zoom in & out?• What format of data will be available / downloadable?• Licensing of the data?• Detailed info or pictures on the pilot sites?• What about the power grid?• How to switch/toggle expert and novice views?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Wind farm icon can be 2 or 3 turbines?• More info buttons• Polygons are not just rectangles & should respect constraints• Add range of numbers & definition to the colour scale on bottom right• 3D layer• Design: round corners (bevel / chamfer)• Export the selected square• Downloads: select by municipality• Grid connection points, capacity vs bottlenecks?• Future scenarios of wind farm deployment• Share the map the user created by link?

WHAT DO YOU LIKE?

+

- TURBINE INFO
- EASY TO NAVIGATE
- ICONS
- SYMBOLS ARE NICE
 - Overview of all layers is good
 - Looks easy to use & intuitive
 - Nice information too
- HEART

WHAT CAN WE IMPROVE?

-

- DOWNLOAD PER REGION
 - distance rates (populations) + link to website (not /region - lol)
- the EV logo and wimby logo could be put together bc. they take to much space
- the wind turbine icon is not super recognizable. it could be improved
- should restrict service or additional info.
- layer: financial compensation/participation for site/owner
- Hand Constraints → should be blocked/optional?
- download per region
 - button/soft for loading pop. / houses / total construction - more detailing?
 - avoided screen
 - improve - looks messy - button meaning - better positioning - scale
 - square with rounded corners

QUESTIONS

- MAP LAYER: WHAT IS DOT AREA?
- EXISTING WIND FARMS BY COUNTRY ONLY?
- how will the results be displayed?
- Scale - to which degree can the zoom in/out?
- licensing of the data?
- what are in the MENU?
- what format of data will be available/downloadable?
- what format of data will be available/downloadable?
- Detailed information on problems on the pilot sites?
- GREYSKALE LEGEND?
- LEGEND FOR MAP LAYERS?

IDEAS

- different icons for peak & turbine
- peak icon can be 2/3 turbine
- more interactive buttons
- 3D view
- Design: round corners (button / chart)
- can a striped angle export and reverse view?
- downloads: select by municipality
- share the map with the user created by link?
- grid connection points, capacity & bottlenecks?
- what about the power grid?
- Future scenarios of wind farm deployment?

Starting the game

Welcome & user guide

End of game

The screenshot shows a web browser window at <https://map.wimby.eu/game>. A modal window titled "The WIMBY scoreboard" is displayed over a map. The modal contains the following text and table:

You selected a location 20km from the ideal location. You scored 500 points and are on place 10 in the scoreboard. Enter your name below to save your place in the scoreboard. Check out the top 3 below.

Place	Name	Score
1	Anonymous wind developer	1001
2	Luis	999
3	Andrea	992
10	you	500

Below the table is an input field and an "Enter name" button. The map background shows a location marked with a red square and a dashed arrow indicating a 20 km distance to a white circle. A scale bar at the bottom right shows 200km and 100km. A "Funded by the European Union" logo is visible in the bottom left corner.

Saved simulations

The screenshot shows a web browser window at <https://map.wimby.eu/profile>. The page displays a user profile with a circular avatar containing the letter 'N'. The main content area is titled "Saved simulations" and includes a search bar and a table of simulation records.

Date	Title	Link	Actions
1/17/2024	Wind farm in Vienna	https://wimby.eu/windf...	Share
1/17/2024	Wind farm in Leuven	https://wimby.eu/windf...	Share
1/17/2024	Wind farm in Styria	https://wimby.eu/windf...	Share

The left sidebar contains navigation options: "Personal Info" and "Saved simulations". A "Menu" icon is located in the top right corner.

<p>What do you like...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We like the game, something good to start with • It looks like a game • No registration to play the game • Scoreboard rocks, good idea! • We like the steps instruction • Intuitive • Share the link of saved simulations is great! 	<p>What can be improved...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain difference between general and pro • Fireworks for winner • Add some clarification of terms / explanation (what is land use change?) • A better story line for the game => you are the new EC president help us achieve the EU wind targets • Add button to "skip" introduction • "Impacts" with the bird icon can be misleading (work on icons shall be careful) • Clone & edit previous simulations • Score composition => weighed for all criteria not only distance! • Remove "pro" from icon? - seems like a payed user • Save an area as favourite
<p>Questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you have to create an account to do the game? • How do you win? When does the game end? • Does it only work in English? • What does education mean? Student/teacher? Which level? • Do we include more map layers? E.g. population map • Depending on level employ different KPI's and indicators • Show how the game is scored? 	<p>Ideas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make the "explanation" of the game more interactive • "Random facts" about renewable energy can pop up • Choose between teacher & student in welcome screen • Set time limit to do the game? • Add progress bar? • Add some pictures of real existing wind farms • In the same results page, next to the scores, we could indicate the amount of CO₂ saved • Be able to visualize the wind farm of others in the score board • Compete to design the best performant (and least annoying) wind park in a particular region • Re-open your old project & edit function missing?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Save the game and be able to continue later• Would be nice if the teacher can change the game settings / goals• Game: EU targets as goals• Welcome: should start with "create wind farm or see current situation"• Guiding questions for new sign-up users to understand the level basic/advanced• 2 modes of the game: speed track = 8 min to pin the optimal farm strategy track = can take as long as possible
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WHAT DO YOU LIKE?

- looks like a game
- some of the icons
- COOL to start with a GAME
- NO registration to play game
- SCORE board Rocks!! good idea
- We like the steps instruction
- We like the game!
- there is a link of what situation is great!
- Impulsive

WHAT CAN WE IMPROVE?

- explain the difference between ground & you
- fireworks for winner
- wind resource & energy should one the score
- add some terms/paraphrase (equivalent is said in the course)
- A better strong line for the game (I know the how to play, please let help to adjust the score)
- add better "skip" introduction
- "Impacts" of the... best you can be meaning
- REMOVE EDITING... MORE SIMILARITIES
- score composition/weighted for all criteria, not only distance
- Remove "pro" from icon - seems like a bit out
- a bit too static -> more people often
- SAVEGAME AS AVAILABLE

QUESTIONS

- how does the scoring work
- do you have to create an account to do the game?
- how do you win? When does the game end?
- does it only work in english?
- what does education mean? (student? teacher? which level?)
- Show how is the game scored?
- Do we include more map layers? e.g. population map
- depending on level employ different KPIs and indicators.

IDEAS

- Add "looseness" usage!
- make the "explanation" of the game more interactive
- the welcome window: choose between teacher & student
- add some patterns of not existing wind farms
- re-open your old project & add -> function missing?
- add time and to do the game?
- add progress bar!
- can pop up!
- add some progress bar!
- could be to loop the first part of the game
- Be able to visualize the wind farm of the score board
- 2 modes of the game speed that can be in the option menu
- save the game and be able to continue later
- would be nice if the teacher can change the game settings/goals
- giving questions for new sign-up users to understand the goal
- WELCOME: create WP OR SEE CURRENT SITUATION
- Multi-player mode: play against your friends

